

The Level of Consumer Confidence in the Purchase Decision of Hotel and Restaurant Tourism Products

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ABSTRACT: The existence of the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the tourism industry, including the purchase of hotel and restaurant services. This study aims to determine the level of consumer confidence in purchasing decisions for hotel and restaurant tourism products. The research method used is descriptive quantitative with a questionnaire instrument and data collection techniques using questionnaires, interviews. The population used in this study is respondents who use hotel and restaurant services in Jabodetabek with various demographics of the work of trainers, consultants and practitioners, but preferably 90 people who are accustomed to using these services. The sample used is saturated sample, so that the entire population becomes a sample of 90 respondents. The results showed that the coefficient of determination or R Square was 0.766. that is, the variable under study explains 76.6% and the remaining 23.4% is explained by other variables not examined in this study. The results of the research on the level of consumer confidence in the decision to purchase hotel and restaurant products during the Covid 19 pandemic, obtained a determination coefficient value of 76.6%. It can be concluded that the level of consumer confidence in purchasing decisions during the Covid 19 period. Consumers who decide to purchase hotel and restaurant tourism products for the purpose of work, travel, and refreshing or traveling. The purpose of purchasing hotel tourism products is dominant with the aim of West Java as much as 27%. Meanwhile, the destination for purchasing restaurant tourism products is dominant in the Jakarta area as much as 33%. Hotel and restaurant service providers continue to use the application of health protocols.

KEYWORDS: level of trust, purchase decisions, hotels, restaurants

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has made many changes for people around the world. The tourism industry was very closely affected due to the Covid 19 pandemic. The existence of a large-scale social restriction policy made people not dare to carry out activities that were gathered in nature. The level of consumer confidence has decreased, because the imposition of new habits in the new normal era is taken into consideration. Tourism products such as hotels and restaurants to support tourism. The desire and trust of consumers to use hotel and restaurant services with various considerations. The hotel industry during the Covid 19 pandemic decreased by 80%. However, after the new normal era, the hotel industry has gradually begun to reactivate. Mayer et al in Listyorini (2015) states that the level of consumer confidence can be categorized into Benefit, Ability, Integrity.

Pramezuary, et al., (2021), there is a decline in terms of consumer 'purchasing decisions', especially during the Covid-19 period. Even though Starbucks is the largest coffee shop brand in the world. However, Starbucks, especially in Indonesia, continues to make various efforts such as sales promotions that are given every day in various forms, especially during a pandemic. The decision to buy restaurant products or restaurant service users during the Covid 19 pandemic does have many considerations. There is a CHSE policy by the government to increase consumer confidence in using tourism products. Kemenkraf (2020), CHSE certification is the process of granting certificates to tourism businesses, tourism destinations and other tourism products to guarantee tourists to the implementation of cleanliness, health, safety and environmental sustainability. With the implementation of the CHSE certification policy, it is hoped that it can increase public confidence and purchasing decisions on tourism products.

The decision to buy restaurant services is the closest target of the community to refreshing during the Covid 19 pandemic. Because the restaurant is not far from the location where the community lives. Restaurants are used as a place to gather, discuss, and stay in touch with friends, family, business, refreshing, and so on. However, what kind of restaurant did the public trust during the Covid 19 pandemic. The use of hotel services during the Covid 19 pandemic has become a consideration for the community to use it, so there are several criteria that the community has for using hotel services.

Kotler (2005) states that the decision to buy made by the buyer is actually a collection of a number of decisions. Consumers have the decision to buy due to various considerations, such as products offered, price, facilities, and cleanliness. Because during the Covid 19 pandemic, cleanliness was a major consideration. Sutisna (2012) states that purchasing decisions consist of indicators:

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benefit association, purchase priority, purchase frequency. Prabela, et al., (2016) research results, if a product with a brand image that is not good in the view of visitors, then the visitor's purchasing decision for the product will also be lower, even though brand image is not one of the determining variables to choose and get visitors to buy the product. and services, but the brand image variable plays an important role in making visitors choose and buy the company's products and services.

Susilawati (2020) states that the service concept has a significant influence on purchasing decisions and income levels in the pre-pandemic period, at the beginning of the pandemic and in the New Normal era. In fact, based on the results of interviews with several café managers who applied the concept of online services during the early days of the pandemic, they actually experienced purchasing decisions and income levels that were up to 50% higher than before the pandemic period. A study is needed to determine the level of consumer confidence in buying hotel and restaurant tourism products during the Covid pandemic. This research is expected to be a reference and advice for hotels and restaurants in implementing services to consumers during the Covid 19 pandemic, so that they can find out what consumers want to use hotel and restaurant services.

II. METHOD

The research method used in this research is descriptive quantitative with a research instrument using a questionnaire. Data collection techniques using questionnaires and interviews with respondents. The population used in this study is respondents who use hotel and restaurant services in Jabodetabek with various demographics of the work of trainers, consultants and practitioners, but preferably 90 people who are accustomed to using these services.

According to Arikunto (2006: 112) says that "if the subject is less than one hundred, it's better to take all of them so that the research is the population. However, if the number of subjects is large, 10-15% or 15 or more can be taken. " This opinion is in accordance with Roscoe in Sugiyono (2011: 90) "The appropriate sample size in the study is between 30 to 500 samples used. The sample technique used is saturated sample, using the entire population to be the research sample. The sample used was 90 people in this study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research that has been conducted on 90 respondents who use hotel and restaurant services in the Jabodetabek area. The research demographic data obtained shows that the purpose of purchasing hotel tourism products made during the COVID-19 pandemic with the aim of West Java is 27% or 27 respondents, 20% or 20 respondents for Jakarta, 13% or 13 respondents for Bogor. This data is the highest data on the purpose of purchasing hotel tourism products. The largest number of hotel tourism products in West Java, the dominant respondents were Bandung and Bogor. The following is the purpose of purchasing hotels according to respondents:

Diagram 1. The level of destination for hotel purchases

The purpose of purchasing restaurant products was 33% or 33 respondents made purchases at restaurants in Jakarta. The research questionnaire after testing the validity of the statements of X and Y variables, the result is that all questionnaire statements are declared valid. There are in the following table:

Validity test table X

Statement	Correlation Value
X1.1	0.875
X1.2	0.838
X1.3	0.843
X1.4	0.831
X1.5	0.837
X1.6	0.785
X1.7	0.829
X1.8	0.823

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X1.9	0.803
X1.10	0.821
X1.11	0.811

Based on the output above, the correlation value has exceeded the R table value of 0.2072. This means that the X data is valid. The 11 statements used in the questionnaire about the level of consumer confidence were declared valid. While the test for the validity of variable Y is as follows:

Test the validity of the Y variable

Statement	Correlation Value
Y1.1	0.721
Y1.2	0.799
Y1.3	0.800
Y1.4	0.640
Y1.5	0.814
Y1.6	0.663
Y1.7	0.800
Y1.8	0.876
Y1.9	0.880

Based on the output above, the correlation value has exceeded the R table value of 0.3044. This means that the Y statement on the questionnaire is valid. There are 9 statements used in the questionnaire on purchasing decision variables and declared valid. The results of the reliability test on the statement of the X and Y variables based on the calculation results are declared reliable.

Uji reliabilitas variable X

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.782	0.963	12

Cronbach's Alpha value has exceeded 0.60, meaning that the statement on variable Y is reliable. The results of the questionnaire statement on variable X are declared reliable and usable.

Reliability test variable Y

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.782	0.937	10

The results of the research on the level of consumer confidence in the use of hotel and restaurant services are found in 11 indicators. It can be seen in the descriptive statistics table that the highest mean on indicators X1.2 and X1.11 is the mean value of 3.6889. In the ability indicator, namely service providers providing guarantee of satisfaction and safety to visitors, it is stated in the statement "hotels and restaurants provide health protocol tools". Based on the results of research from 90 respondents, the highest mean is in the statement of the availability of health protocol devices, because this is the basis for consumer decisions to buy products provided by hotel and restaurant services. While the smallest mean is found in indicator X1.4, namely the ability indicator in the statement "providing services using health protocol attributes", the mean value is 3.5889. Based on the results of the study, consumers stated that the services provided to consumers got the lowest score on the use of health protocol attributes when serving consumers. Because some hotel and restaurant services do not use health protocol attributes, only masks and faceshilds are used.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
X1.1	90	1.00	5.00	330.00	3.6667	.68696
X1.2	90	2.00	5.00	332.00	3.6889	.68112
X1.3	90	2.00	5.00	329.00	3.6556	.60264
X1.4	90	1.00	5.00	323.00	3.5889	.71727

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X1.5	90	1.00	5.00	325.00	3.6111	.68194
X1.6	90	1.00	5.00	323.00	3.5889	.77741
X1.7	90	1.00	5.00	325.00	3.6111	.74494
X1.8	90	2.00	5.00	335.00	3.7222	.65390
X1.9	90	2.00	5.00	324.00	3.6000	.69992
X1.10	90	1.00	5.00	326.00	3.6222	.68002
X1.11	90	2.00	5.00	332.00	3.6889	.68112
Valid N (listwise)	90					

In variable Y or the purchase decision to use restaurant and hotel services, there is the highest mean value of priority in buying with a mean value of 3.8222, contained in the statement "consumers trust the products provided by hotel and restaurant services. Respondents do not routinely use the hotel and restaurant services they buy, because they buy restaurant and hotel services for work, travel, and refreshing or traveling. So that the lowest value on routine use of hotel and restaurant services, namely the mean value of 3.5667 is the same as the purchase frequency indicator, that respondents do not often purchase hotel and restaurant services during the Covid 19 pandemic. There are some respondents who feel safe cooking their own food and do not use overnight services. in hotels during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Y1.1	90	1.00	5.00	335.00	3.7222	1.07084
Y1.2	90	1.00	5.00	336.00	3.7333	1.04720
Y1.3	90	1.00	5.00	344.00	3.8222	.85562
Y1.4	90	1.00	5.00	337.00	3.7444	1.03382
Y1.5	90	1.00	5.00	332.00	3.6889	.88234
Y1.6	90	1.00	5.00	321.00	3.5667	1.00616
Y1.7	90	1.00	5.00	321.00	3.5667	.88749
Y1.8	90	1.00	5.00	325.00	3.6111	.99091
Y1.9	90	1.00	5.00	321.00	3.5667	1.01727
Valid N (listwise)	90					

In this study, to get the linear regression value, the classical test was used for the statistical requirements that must be met. Classic assumption test 1.

Normality Test

In the results of the histogram test, the curved lines form mountains and look perfect with symmetrical legs, it can be concluded that the data in the study are normally distributed. In the normal probability plots test results, the points follow the diagonal line from point 0 and do not extend too far, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Based on the results of the classic assumption test, research on the level of customer satisfaction on buyer satisfaction has data that is normally distributed and the results can be used as research results.

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Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the study based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test aim to test whether in the regression model there is an unequal variance of residuals between observers. If the variance from one observer residual to another observer remains, it is called homoscedasticity and if it is different it is called heteroscedasticity. Based on the results of the research that the data points spread above and below the 0 (zero) point on the Y and X axes and do not form certain patterns such as zigzags, piling up, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity symptom. Multiple Linear Regression Test

1. The Coefficient of Determination (R Square)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.875 ^a	.766	.763	.36892

a. Predictors: (Constant), X

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Based on the output above, it is known that the coefficient of determination or R Square is 0.766. that is, the variable under study explains 76.6% and the remaining 23.4% is explained by other variables not examined in this study. The results of the research on the level of consumer confidence in the decision to purchase hotel and restaurant products during the Covid 19 pandemic, obtained a determination coefficient value of 76.6%. It can be concluded that the level of consumer confidence in purchasing decisions during the Covid 19 period is equal to the R square value. Meanwhile, 23.4% was influenced by other variables which were not researched. So that further research can be carried out which can influence hotel and restaurant purchasing decisions during the Covid 19 pandemic.

2. Partial Test (T Test)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.555	.252		-2.201	.030
	X	1.160	.068	.875	16.950	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

From the output above, it can be seen that the significance value of the T test at the level of consumer confidence is 0.000 < 0.05, which means that the level of consumer confidence has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Consumers believe in hotel and restaurant service providers by providing various guaranteed protocols for health, cleanliness, facilities, security. This makes consumers trust and use hotel and restaurant services during the Covid 19 pandemic.

IV. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the results of this study that the influence of the level of consumer confidence on purchasing decisions for hotel and restaurant tourism products during the Covid 19 pandemic was 76.6% and the remaining 23.4% was explained by other variables not examined in this study. Consumers believe in hotel and restaurant service providers by providing various guaranteed

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protocols for health, cleanliness, facilities, security. This makes consumers trust and use hotel and restaurant services during the Covid 19 pandemic. Based on the highest indicator of the variable level of consumer confidence, hotel and restaurant service providers implement health protocols, so that consumers believe in deciding to purchase hotels and restaurants. In the purchasing decision variable, the highest indicator is the benefit association. Consumers decide to buy because they make purchases for necessities.

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